
MOBILE TECHNOLOGIES FOR ACADEMIC LIBRARIES: AN OVERVIEW

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Abstract:

The concept of library is changing. Today traditional library has been replaced by virtual library. Today today we see everyone on mobile phone. Mobile phone has become an integral part of our life. Due to mobile technology the world has become very close. Librarians can use this technology to connect with the user provide the right information to the user in less time. This paper highlights mobile technologies, M-library services, Advantages of M-technologies, disadvantages of M-Technologies etc.

Keywords: Mobile Technologies (M-technology), ICT, Digital Libraries, Information Services, e-resources,

Introduction:

Today ICT (Information Communication Technology) has covered the whole world. Today the whole world has come closer to get any information in the world to talk to any person, to know the information of that person today we can contact them with one click. We can get any information in the world with one click and this can only be possible. An example of this is because of Information Communication Technology M- Technology Mobile Phones. The attraction of mobile phones is not only among young people but also among all age groups. By taking advantage of the fact that libraries are being used, libraries can deliver their services to their product users. Users no longer need to go to the

library to get any kind of information and resource, they do not need to take the time of the library, but they can get all these things with a single click. Can contact the library and any Information can be accessed anywhere and anytime in a very short time. The M-technology includes, "iPods, MP3 player. Personal Digital Assistants, USB Drive, E-Book Reader, Smart Phone, Ultra-Mobile PC and Laptop / Tablet PC". Libraries can make use of multimedia messaging service (MMS) on mobile devices to share photos, videos, and audio. Most of the e-book publishers provide 24x7 access to the library subscriptions from any internet terminal within the campus, as well on mobile devices, such as iPods, Android devices, and Kindle.

Mobile Technologies for Library Services:

1. Library Guide Service:

When a user has a query and wants to contact the library and resolve the query, the library guide service through the library can resolve the user's query and help the user as soon as possible.

2. Text Reference Service:

If the library receives a large number of inquiries and needs to respond in a brief, the library may send a link to the article or reference directly.

3. SMS Alert Service:

It is very important services provide by M-technology. Librarian can alert on library timing, new arrivals, overdue, renew books, information about library events & programs, library products. SMS messages can be sent to many users at a time so users can get up to date information within a time.

4. Image Service:

If a user requires a photocopy of a library document, book, journal content page, maps, diagram, rare book photocopy the library can provide the same service for a fee.

5. Database Browsing Service:

A library can provide database access to users through which the user can get the information they want. For

example OPAC.OPAC allows the user to get information about the collection in the library. OCLC World Catalogue mobile application is also an example. And get information about other materials.

6. My Library:

In my library user can get information about the resources of the library. User can renew books, check collection, user can read alerts, set up email notice of new books & journal articles.

Advantages of Implementation of Mobile Technology in Libraries:

1. User participation:

Libraries can enrich OPAC by allowing user-generated content, such as notes or images, to make a mobile-based website more interactive by adding a chat room or library guide.

2. User Friendly:

Today mobile technology is popular among people of all ages, no special training or orientation or preparation is required for it. Mobile users use many facilities on mobiles, for example, SMS, instant messaging, web browsing, e-mail, all these functions are available in mobiles and if not, they can download and use them.

This allows the user to get the right

information in less time and the mobile technology is easy to use.

3. Personalized Service help:

If a user needs any information he can directly contact the library or the librarian the user does not need to go to the library the user can access all the facilities on his mobile for exp. online catalogue, full text article, database access, reference questions via the ask a librarian service.

4. Time Saving:

If the user wants any kind of library facility, they don't need to go to the library or wait, they can operate through M-technology, get information about the resources available in the library and reserve the required resources.

5. Access to Print: Disabled users:

By using the talking software in the mobile phone visually impaired or physically handicapped user can also use library services.

6. Unlimited Access:

User can get unlimited information or e-resources and journal article from mobile phone.

Conclusion:

In today's world mobile, smartphones are very widespread. The attraction of mobile technology is not only seen among young students but also among people of all ages. Due to mobile

technology, we can access any information in the world in less time and reach the desired people. Librarians can benefit from their events and programs. Mobile technology can be used to convey information about services to the user. Due to mobile technology, the user can get the information he wants in a short time, at the place he wants, with one click. By using mobile technology, the library can provide many services, for example, SMS notification service, document service, library guide. Service, QR Code Service.

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